
MYTHICAL EUGENICS. THE MACEDONIAN-AMAZON ROYAL ALLIANCE IN CLASSICAL SOURCES

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ABSTRACT:

The most well-known Amazon stories exhibit a number of common characteristics, most notably their ultimate defeat at the hands of a legendary male hero. Even those narratives in which such characters did not achieve the same degree of renown as Heracles, Theseus or Achilles, as in the case of Bellerophon, or those who were not even granted a Hellenic origin, as in the case of the young Priam, the most important of these premises is fulfilled: they were all characters as mythical as the Amazons themselves. However, the case of Alexander III of Macedon presents particularities that are not linked to the historical character of the main character, but rather to the time in which this story arose (4th century BC), which is much later than the traditional heroic texts. This tale is atypical and marks a significant turning point in the Amazon mythological tradition. Despite the growing prominence of the Macedonian ruler, there is no direct representation of this encounter. Indirect references to it emerge only at a relatively late stage in the tradition. This article will analyse the classical sources dedicated to this legendary encounter in order to ascertain the reasons behind its invention.

RESUMEN: EUGENESIA MÍTICA. LA ALIANZA REAL MACEDONIO-AMAZÓNICA EN LAS FUENTES CLÁSICAS

Los relatos amazónicos más conocidos muestran una serie de características comunes entre las que destaca su derrota final a manos de un héroe masculino legendario. Incluso aquellos en los que tales personajes no alcanzaron el mismo renombre que Heracles, Teseo o Aquiles, como sucede con Belerofonte, o a los que ni siquiera se les otorgaba un origen heleno, caso del joven Príamo, se cumple la más importante de estas premisas, todos ellos eran personajes tan míticos como las propias amazonas. No obstante, el caso de Alejandro III de Macedonia presenta particularismos vinculados no al carácter histórico del personaje protagonista, y relacionados con el momento en que surgió este relato (s. IV a.C.), muy posterior a los textos heroicos tradicionales. Nos encontramos aquí con un relato atípico que marca un hito en el universo mítico amazónico, por cuanto a pesar de la relevancia que adquirió el soberano macedonio, no conocemos una sola representación dedicada a este encuentro, y solo en algún caso podríamos intuir esa relación de manera indirecta en un momento muy tardío. En este artículo analizaremos las fuentes clásicas dedicadas a este legendario encuentro para descubrir los motivos que llevaron a su invención.

KEYWORDS: Alexander, Talestris, Amazons, mythology, eugenics.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Alejandro, Talestris, amazonas, mitología, eugenesia.

1. Introduction

The encounter between Alexander and Queen Thalestris is of interest for a number of reasons, not least because it offers the possibility of assigning a precise chronology to the supposed Amazon presence in a period much later than that in which we could place most of his stories. These are always set in a remote mythical past¹, which we might place around the 2nd millennium BC. Furthermore, it is the only known reference to the carnal encounter between these legendary warriors and a historical figure.

A number of authors have proposed that the Amazon people disappeared as a result of their involvement in the Trojan conflict.² This is on the grounds that they were unable to defend themselves against their neighbours

¹ Sanchez Sanz 2017, 146.

² D. S. 2. 46; Sen. *Tro.* 236; while Isocrates (4. 68-70) or Ammianus (22.8) allude to the Athenian campaign.

following the significant military casualties they sustained in the preceding Athenian campaign and at Troy. Both events are believed to have occurred in close chronological proximity.³ If we were to accept the chronology that places the Trojan episode in the 13th century BC, this would imply the survival of the Amazon kingdom for almost a millennium until the time of Alexander. Indeed, the Alexandrian narrative does not even place its end at that time, which would serve to extend its mythical existence in an indeterminate manner. This indirectly affirms the exaggeration inherent in the accounts advocating its demise, which was probably intended to confer greater prestige upon its architects.

Nevertheless, it is equally accurate to observe that there is a paucity of narratives pertaining to Amazon history that are situated chronologically between the end of the heroic age and the era of Alexander. It is notable that Xenophon does not make any reference to these events during the time of Cyrus⁴, despite the assertion by Diodorus that an earlier encounter between the Amazons and Cyrus the Great occurred during the 6th century BC.⁵ Furthermore, there is no evidence of any artistic representation of this encounter. The only known depiction of Alexander and the Amazons in the same context is a medallion from the Roman period (200-250 AD), discovered in Abukir, Egypt (200-250 AD).⁶ The obverse depicts the bust of Caracalla, while the reverse portrays the Macedonian ruler seated before the goddess Nike, holding a shield inscribed with the combat between Achilles and Penthesilea. This is strikingly similar to the shield found in Tomb II of Vergina, which belonged to Philip II of Macedon. The two narratives, separated by centuries in the Greek collective imaginary, bear no resemblance to one another. However, this does not preclude the possibility that some form of artistic representation may have existed.

In any case, the Alexandrian version is evidently an attempt to utilise the Amazon universe with the objective of enhancing its prestige, in a manner analogous to that which occurred with the Greek heroes.⁷ This is because their eastern campaign provided the ideal rationale for such an endeavour. While the Amazons are depicted as the traditional adversaries, they ultimately consented to this encounter as a means of perpetuating their lineage, convinced of the advantages that the Macedonian sovereign could offer through eugenics.

2. Source analysis

The issue that arises with this legend is the lack of information about the known sources. While Plutarch provides a list of authors who mentioned it in their writings during the 4th century BC, we have no knowledge about most of them. Furthermore, the remaining allusions are either fragmentary or very brief, which significantly limits the available information. However, this does offer insight into the potential extent of lost traditions that may have existed about the Amazon universe.⁸

One such figure is Philo the Theban, whose association with the individual who lived between the 5th and 4th centuries BC is untenable given that Alexander had not yet been born. The same is true of numerous other authors whose identities remain unknown in this account, including Origen, Philip of Theangela, Istro, Hecataeus of Eretria, and Philip of Chalcis. In some cases, we can discern the authors' homelands, but little else is known about them, except that they lived between the 4th century BC and the 2nd century AD. He also mentions a Ptolemy, who may correspond to the Alexandrian grammarian Ptolemy Quenus, a contemporary of his. Regarding those of whom we have some knowledge, we find the following: the close friend of Alexander and author of a history of his life, Cares of Mytilene, as well as the historian and geographer, Polyclitus of Larissa, who lived in the 4th century BC. In addition, the following authors are known to us from this period: the grammarian and historian Antikyrides of Athens and the Greek historian Duris of Samos (both from the 4th to the 3rd century BC); the historian Clitarchus of Alexandria and the historian and philosopher who accompanied Alexander on his campaigns, Onesicritus (both from the 3rd century BC); and the philosopher Aristobulus of Alexandria (from the 2nd century BC).

Indeed, numerous authors have referenced this legendary narrative, a character that many of them have ardently defended, to the extent that they constitute the majority against the known historical sources that have corroborated its veracity. This is analogous to other Amazon episodes in the Hellenistic collective imaginary. The list was undoubtedly much longer, as in other cases, but here Plutarch only mentions them to demonstrate his erudition and to offer a kind of "state of the art" in antiquity that pitted detractors and supporters of giving any credence to this

³ Thrasyll. Mend. *FHG*. 3. 503. 3.

⁴ X. *An.* 4.

⁵ D. S. 2. 44-46. In fact, he refers to the Scythians, but places their society in the hands of women, whom he finally refers to as Amazons. They would be led by an unnamed queen whom Herodotus (1. 205-214) identifies as Tomiris without assigning her Amazon status.

⁶ Bode-Museum 18200021, BM-03505, 18200021.

⁷ Sanchez Sanz 2023, 3.

⁸ Plu. *Alex.* 46.

account. Some scholars were unconvinced by the veracity of the narrative, including Duris of Samos, Hecataeus of Eretria and Philip of Chalcis. In contrast, other academics such as Clitarchus, Onesicritus, Polyclitus, Origen and Istro were more receptive to its claims.

In any case, the texts of the authors mentioned by Plutarch who were contemporaries of Alexander himself are not available to us. Consequently, our first direct source for this account dates from the 1st century BC, namely Pompeius Trogo, through Justin.⁹ He is among those who defended the veracity of the encounter between Alexander and the Amazons, which he claims as proof that these warriors had survived. However, in consideration of the casualties incurred in previous instances, he is convinced that it must have been a significant exertion and sacrifice, particularly given their limited numbers. It seems reasonable to posit that Trogo accorded the same veracity to the stories of Herakles, Theseus, Achilles, and so forth as he did to the accounts of the constant clashes between the Amazons and neighbouring peoples¹⁰, except for the ritual encounters aimed at perpetuating their lineage.¹¹

Trogo is the first to identify the Amazon queen at this time as Thalestris, stating that she was also known as Minithia.¹² He provides no details regarding the events preceding the meeting with Alexander, stating directly that they spent thirteen days together with the objective of the queen conceiving a daughter with such a renowned individual. If we accept the traditional view that the Amazon society was matriarchal¹³, it seems plausible that they reached a mutually beneficial agreement. If the child was female, she would remain among the Amazons; if male, he would be given to his father as his heir, in accordance with the precedent established with the Gargarians.¹⁴ Trogo provides minimal additional insight, noting that following this period, the queen returned to her homeland. It is evident that she was certain of her pregnancy, yet she perished shortly thereafter, leaving the outcome unconfirmed. However, the implication that with her the hope of the Amazons died suggests that the outcome was not positive for anyone. Indeed, it may be the case that the Amazons were already in such a difficult situation that they were unable to survive as a people. It appears that only a daughter born of such distinguished ancestors could potentially restore them to their former glory. Without her, however, they ultimately succumbed to their enemies. In any case, this is an unusual episode in Amazon historiography, not only for the reasons mentioned above, but also due to the absence of any confrontation, even though the end result was the same.

Diodorus, a contemporary of Trogo, also sought to cite this account (1st century BC) in order to assist in delineating what may have been his most renowned iteration.¹⁵ Indeed, he also makes reference to the period of thirteen days during which the protagonists dedicated themselves to their shared mission, presumably in accordance with the same tradition, referring to the Amazon queen only as Thalestris. As previously discussed, Diodorus positioned the Amazon territory between Thermodon and Tanais¹⁶, encompassing the Pontus and Colchis region up to Lake Meotis. However, he did not specify the location of the meeting, given that the route taken by the Macedonian was distant from these areas. The most proximate locations on his itinerary were Gordius (Phrygia)¹⁷ and Ancyra.¹⁸ With respect to Thermodon, these sites were situated at a considerable distance from the kingdom of the Amazons, whether or not the latter was located in closer proximity to the Phasis. The same is true of the sites of the battles of Issos or Gaugamela¹⁹, should one assume that the Amazons were situated in a more southerly location. Furthermore, Diodorus indicates that the meeting occurred after the campaign against the Mardes (ca. 330 BC), whose traditional kingdom was situated to the southwest of Hyrcania.²⁰ This was a considerable distance from the Amazon territory, exceeding the distance to Ancyra, which had been conquered several years earlier (333 BC).

It is evident that those who advocated for the continued existence of the Amazon kingdom in northern Pontus are now confronted with mounting uncertainty. To substantiate their claim, they would have had to traverse the formidable Caucasus Mountain range towards Hyrcania, a perilous journey²¹ for the relatively small group of Amazons who appear to have undertaken the expedition. Diodorus attributes the same intention to Thalestris, who became the Amazon's hope for the survival of her people. She was capable of giving birth to a heiress who would

⁹ Iust. *Epit.* 2. 32-33.

¹⁰ They are identified as the cause of their final demise (D. S. 2. 46).

¹¹ Lys. 2. 4-6; D. S. 2. 45.

¹² Iust. *Epit.* 2. 33.

¹³ Plu. *Pomp.* 35; Philostr. *Her.* 23, 56-57; Str. 11. 5. 1-3; Flavius Arianus of Nicomedia *FHG.* 3. 597. 58; Iust. *Epit.* 2. 3 and probably Metrodorus of Scepsis (FGH. 3. 204. 4) in placing the Gargarians as their neighbours.

¹⁴ Metrodorus of Scepsis *FGH.* 3. 204. 4; Str. 11. 5. 1-3; Iust. *Epit.* 2. 4.

¹⁵ D. S. 17. 77. 1-3.

¹⁶ D. S. 2. 44-46.

¹⁷ Arr. *An.* 2. 3.

¹⁸ Curt. 3. 1, 22-24.

¹⁹ Plu. *Alex.* 24; Arr. *An.* 3. 8, 7.

²⁰ Arr. *An.* 3. 24, 1-2; Curt. 6. 5, 11-21; D. S. 17. 76, 3-8; Plu. *Alex.* 44. 3-5.

²¹ Sanchez Sanz 2021, 10.

stand out for her *areté* as a result of such progenitors. Alexander accepted, reasoning that the Amazons' reputed beauty and strength would provide him with a suitable heir if he were male.²² Once more, following this period, the queen departed without providing any indication of her success, although it may be reasonably inferred that she was successful. Additionally, she states that she appeared before the Macedonians accompanied by hundreds of her companions²³, which could be interpreted as a demonstration of power before the Macedonians or a result of the dangers she had to overcome on her journey. Nevertheless, Thalestris prohibited her Amazons from interacting with the soldiers in order to prevent any potential incidents. Although Diodorus does not provide details regarding the outcome of this encounter, it seems that he believes it had significant consequences for Alexander himself.²⁴ From this point onward, Alexander began to adopt Persian customs.

Strabo is another author who makes reference to this encounter in the 1st century BC. However, his account is merely testimonial in nature and driven by a desire to present his opinion on the subject. In this way, he offers an example of the numerous nonsensical legends that could be created around the great figures of history.²⁵ Nevertheless, he once more identifies the queen as Thalestris and adds that, should the episode have occurred, it must have done so in a location proximate to that suggested by Diodorus, although he does not specify the precise temporal context. Similarly, Plutarch's account indicates that there were others who shared this scepticism, noting that the most reliable biographers of the Macedonian ruler never made any reference to this encounter. Among the authors who mention this encounter is Clitarchus of Alexandria (3rd century BC).²⁶ However, he maintains his opinion despite placing the Amazonian kingdom at the Caspian Gates, on the western shore of the Caspian Sea, which is much closer to Hyrcania than Thermodon itself.

It is evident that at this juncture, the knowledge of the Pontus region was sufficiently advanced to negate the presence of any Amazon indication. This may be the reason why numerous authors have posited its previous extinction, while others hypothesise that its domain must have been situated further afield, in the vicinity of the Caspian. This is indicative of the expansion of the boundaries of the known world and the concomitant shift in the status of the kingdoms and mythical beings that existed within it. Strabo does not provide any indication as to the duration of the two protagonists' union, nor does he offer any insight into the outcome of their relationship, given that he himself acknowledges the existence of conflicting accounts.

In the 1st century AD, there is an allusion to the Alexandrian grammarian Ptolemy Quenus in Plutarch, as well as an account by Quintus Curtius Rufus. The similarity between this account and that of Diodorus suggests that they may have been based on a common source.²⁷ He situates the events in the same historical period, after the campaign against the Mardes, within the same region and with the same number of Amazons accompanying Thalestris. However, he also states that a considerable number remained stationed at the border of their territory, attempting to conceal the perceived deficiencies that other authors have attributed to them at this juncture. It is notable that he specifies the extent of his kingdom, which extended from Thermodon to Phasis. This vast territory would not have been diminished by the actions of his neighbours. The appellation ascribed to the queen is as canonical as that of Penthesilea herself.

The potential locations for the meeting include Zadracarra, the capital of Hyrcania, where Darius owned a palace that was used as a residence for the lovers.²⁸ Indeed, although he initially asserts that the queen's objective remained the pursuit of progeny, following their encounter, a profound affection emerged between them. This phenomenon bears resemblance to the potential outcomes that might have transpired between Theseus and Antiope or Achilles and Penthesilea had they been extant. The author employs a number of conventional stereotypes in his portrayal of the queen, including an allusion to the cauterisation of her right breast and a description of her attire²⁹, which is typical of the period and leaves her anatomy uncovered. She is depicted as armed with two javelins, a bow and an axe. Furthermore, he asserts that she was taller than Alexander himself, stating that for the Amazons, height was a symbol of greatness. Consequently, Rufus claims that Thalestris, who was expecting a Macedonian equal to or even taller than herself, was taken aback.³⁰ Alexander was similarly impressed and, cognizant of their renown, attempted to incorporate them into his army but was ultimately unsuccessful. The objective of Thalestris was

²² Q. S. 6. 241–245.

²³ Another recurring element of the story, also indicated by Pseudo-Chalithenes (3. 26).

²⁴ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 172.

²⁵ Str. 11. 5. 4.

²⁶ Whom other authors already considered exaggerated (Quint. *Inst.* 10. I. 74; Cic. *Brut.* 2).

²⁷ Curt. 6. 5. 24–32.

²⁸ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 172–174.

²⁹ Sanchez Sanz 2014, 33.

³⁰ Alexander's small stature was well known, so perhaps he was trying to add veracity to the story. Olaguer-Feliú (2000, 77) assumes that Alexander would have been around 1.67 cm tall based on the references provided by Curtius Rufus, which would actually be within the average height of the time.

distinct, and Rufus provides an account of the arrangements made for this transitional union. If the child was female, she would become the heir to the Amazon throne; if male, he would be given to her father to occupy the Macedonian throne.³¹

Following the conclusion of the match, Thalestris returned to Themyscira without providing any assurances regarding the success of her mission. It was undoubtedly a lengthy journey to reach the Macedonian, though it was always a shorter distance than that which they had previously traversed to reach Athens. Nevertheless, he erroneously places it near the border with Hyrcania, perhaps due to a lack of geographical knowledge or to reduce the considerable distance that separated them. Rufus is reluctant to express his personal opinion on the veracity of the story, but concurs with Diodorus in considering it the reason for the change in the habits of Philip's son. This appears to indicate that they exerted a negative influence, or at the very least, were responsible for the loss of a cultural identity that they considered superior. Nevertheless, no tradition mentions that the same thing occurred with Theseus, despite the fact that they lived together for a longer period of time and had children.³²

Ovid (1st century BC-1st century AD), originally from Sulmona in Italy but exiled to Tomis following a dispute with Augustus, was able to gain insight into the local traditions associated with the Amazon mythical universe. This resulted in the creation of a unique type of Amazon coinage³³, which has been documented as existing during the reign of Heliogabalus. In his commentary, it becomes evident that the distinction between Alexander and Thalestris was not solely attributed to the Macedonian, as the latter compares all women of considerable height to Amazons³⁴, a detail that is not frequently highlighted. It is evident that the Amazons were typically portrayed as exceedingly beautiful³⁵, with Homer himself describing them as agile.³⁶ These attributes collectively contributed to an even more formidable image.³⁷ Each and every one of their qualities had to be outstanding; otherwise, they would not have been perceived as a fearsome and worthy adversary to the Greek heroes.

In the period between the 1st and 2nd centuries AD, it is appropriate to recall Plutarch and the limited information he provides, despite making reference to the controversy that arose concerning the veracity of an account that Alexander himself denied.³⁸ Additionally, Plutarch notes that the Amazon queen was aware of Alexander's fame and even possessed knowledge of the route taken by the Macedonian army to meet him. However, he notes that in one of his letters to Antipater, in which he informed him of the progress of the expedition, he only indicated that the Scythian king had offered him his daughter in marriage, without ever mentioning the Amazons. It is noteworthy that the classical sources again depict a new relationship between the Scythians and the Amazons, albeit in an indirect manner. Plutarch himself suggests that the origin of this myth may have arisen from such an encounter.

In 339 BC, Philip II had already confronted the Scythian king Ateas. One of his daughters subsequently became the wife of a Macedonian³⁹, and it is possible that this was the same individual whose remains were discovered in the antechamber of Vergina's Tomb II.⁴⁰ In 329 BC, Alexander encountered the Scythians once more at the Iaxartes (Syr-Daria) river⁴¹, where their leader proposed a marriage alliance between his daughter and Alexander, invoking the precedent set by the previous encounter between their respective fathers. However, the Scythians were ultimately vanquished. Diodorus himself placed the encounter with Thalestris around 330 BC, which seems to corroborate Plutarch's assertion. The account concludes with the introduction of a new detail that serves to reinforce its implausibility.⁴² He states that when Onesicritus read the passage devoted to this meeting to Lysimachus, the latter responded with a laugh and enquired: "Where was I at that time?"

In the initial period of the second century AD, Arrian recounts this episode in the context of Ptolemy and Aristobulus, as well as in the words of other authors such as Onesicritus.⁴³ His account is distinct from those

³¹ It should be remembered that at the time of the encounter Alexander had not yet met Roxana and had no offspring (Arr. An. 4. 19).

³² Theseus did not have the celebrity of Herakles, nor was he actually Athenian by birth (his origin is disputed but seems to be more associated with Crete, Valdés Guía 1994, 370), but he was the local hero of Marathon and Aphidna, son of Aegeus, of the dynasty of the Erechtidæ, to whom two essential events in the development of Athens were attributed: the *synesthesia* of Attica and the establishment of democracy (Valdés Guía 2000, 37).

³³ Tomis (218-222 d.C.), AMNG (Antiken Münzen Nord-Griechenlands) 3080; Moushmov 2078; Varbanov 5202.

³⁴ Ou. Am. 2. 4.

³⁵ As e.g. in Philostratus (*Her.* 14.1-2).

³⁶ Hom. *Il.* 2. 814.

³⁷ As opposed to the traditional consideration of Greek women (Sanchez Sanz 2020, 19-20).

³⁸ Plu. *Alex.* 46.

³⁹ Str. 7.3.

⁴⁰ Sanchez Sanz 2013, 137-138.

⁴¹ Curt. 7. 8, 12-30. Although its traditional territory was far away, in the present-day Ukraine (Sanchez Sanz 2024a, 178).

⁴² Plu. *Alex.* 46.

⁴³ Arr. An. 7. 13.

previously discussed, as he states that the satrap of Media, Atrophates, sent Alexander one hundred Amazons. It seems reasonable to posit that this gift was intended to ingratiate the satrap with the conqueror, although the text does not explain how he was in a position to do so. In this instance, the episode is situated temporally shortly before the demise of Hephaestion.⁴⁴ This chronological placement is later than that indicated by Diodorus, and consequently, the location is more distant from the Amazon kingdom, given that the expedition was progressing towards India. He describes them as wearing cavalry uniforms, equipped with axes and peltas, which are also typically Amazonian elements.

Atropates was also a notable figure who, perhaps cognizant of Alexander's penchant for epic narratives, sought to bestow upon him a fitting and unexpected gift. It is unclear whether the satrap genuinely believed that Alexander would be convinced by such a performance. However, if his intention was to provide a hundred Amazon-like women for the occasion, then we can grant him some credibility in this regard. This would explain the sources' creation of this legendary episode. It is noteworthy that Atropates was not only conversant with the mythical Amazon universe but also aware that the Greeks would anticipate encountering such warriors in Asia Minor, which would serve to disguise the deception. Indeed, he was well aware of the traditional Amazon appearance and symbolism through other accounts or iconography. However, it should be noted that the Amazon use of hoplitic equipment was more prevalent in Archaic pieces than even in the Hellenistic period. Arrian himself offers a critique of the satrap, stating that the weapons in question did not align with the conventional Amazon image.⁴⁵ However, it is evident that at this juncture, Arrian's assessment pertains more to the satrap's equipment than to his weaponry. This is because the pelta, the labrys, and the sagaris were recurrent elements in written sources and Amazon scenes up to the Roman era.⁴⁶

It is evident that a considerable number of narratives pertaining to the Amazon mythological realm were already well-known among the Medes, given that their empire extended to territories where some sources had previously identified the presence of Amazon authority, particularly in regions situated to the south of Pontus, the Caucasus, or even in Hyrcania. Nevertheless, the accounts prevalent in the Near East may have differed, if not in their essentials, then at least in some particulars, from those current in the West, and thus a distinct prototype of the Amazon may have been formulated, although it would still be regarded as part of the traditional corpus of information.

It is unclear whether Alexander came to believe that they were genuine Amazons. Even when dressed as such, these Medes would have had little or no connection to the physical characteristics typically associated with Amazons. Nevertheless, despite the considerable challenges, it appears that they were meticulously selected and rigorously trained women, as evidenced by the lesser development and exposure of their right breasts, which adds to the overall realism⁴⁷. It seems reasonable to posit that the satrap wished to attend to every detail, aware that if the deception were discovered, it could incite the ire of the Macedonian ruler. It seems unlikely that Atropates ever intended to deceive Alexander. Rather, it is probable that his intention was merely to offer the Macedonian ruler a theatrical representation of the wonders associated with the territories in question, as these were the themes that were commonly explored in Greek mythology.

In any case, Alexander resolved to accept the gift and integrate them into his army with the intention of enhancing his prestige in the forthcoming campaigns. However, their presence provoked such a commotion among his troops that he was compelled to abandon this plan.⁴⁸ It is possible that he genuinely believed them to be Amazons, as Arrian records that he sought to meet their queen with the intention of begetting a worthy heir, rather than the other way around as is commonly depicted in other traditions. It is noteworthy that Atrophates designated one of them as sovereign, despite the fact that numerous renowned Amazons have been recorded as occupying such a role. It is not implausible that Alexander made this decision, given that he had not yet designated a successor. The birth of a progeny would have conferred considerable prestige upon him, thereby removing any doubts about his right to the throne. In any case, there is no indication of the queen's possible birth, nor is there any information regarding the fate of the warriors after they were removed from the Macedonian army.

Arrian ultimately expresses scepticism about the account he has just presented, not only aligning with the perspectives of the aforementioned authors but also considering it implausible that the Amazon culture could have persisted until the 4th century BC. He recalls that Xenophon makes no mention of them between the 5th and 4th centuries BC⁴⁹, which further supports this scepticism. Nevertheless, the same statement indicates that he at

⁴⁴ Occurred at Ecbatana ca. 324 BC. (Arr. *An.* 7.14).

⁴⁵ Perhaps referring to their attested use of spears or *aspis* (Ps. Apollod. *Epit.* 2. 9; Str. 11. 5. 1; D. S. 3. 52; Q. S. 1. 568–574).

⁴⁶ Verg. *Aen.* 1. 488–493; Hellanicus cfr. Tz. *AH.* 22; X. *An.* 4. Pausanias (1. 42) even states that Hippolyta's tomb at Megara was in the form of a pelta.

⁴⁷ Arr. *An.* 7. 13.

⁴⁸ Arr. *An.* 7. 13.

⁴⁹ Arr. *An.* 7. 13. Even less so if, as he explains, the soldiers of the Anabasis passed through Trebizond, where Arrian places his

least entertained the notion of their existence in the remote past. According to the account, Atrophates sought to impress Alexander by capturing a group of women from a barbarian village in his vicinity and equipping them in the Amazonian manner to lend credibility to his narrative. It is notable that he did not require them to learn how to fight, given his assertion regarding the existence of female warriors in certain cultures. However, he did necessitate the imparting of equestrian skills, a crucial competency among the Amazons. It seems reasonable to posit that he was thinking of the Scythian or Sarmatian peoples, given their reputation as excellent horsemen.⁵⁰

In the third century AD, Pseudo-Calisthenes presented his interpretation of the narrative in several fragments that are not aligned with the preceding accounts. In the initial account, Pseudo-Calisthenes refers to the encounter between Alexander and Candaules, the son of Queen Candace. This is another legendary episode for which the setting is unknown.⁵¹ Following the assault by the Bebrices, the prince elected to seek refuge within the Macedonian encampment, wherein he informed the ruler of his intention to embark on a journey to the land of the Amazons, where he would engage in a mystic rite.⁵² No further information is available regarding this unpublished account in the Amazon world, nor about the purpose of the ceremony. No source has confirmed the existence of this type of cult among the Amazons, let alone that a foreign male was permitted to participate. The source of this information is unclear, as the Bébrices were a legendary people of Thracian origin who were settled in Bithynia and defeated by Heracles at the same time as he supposedly confronted the Amazons⁵³. It is evident that the mention of these figures was intended to establish a connection with a heroic past that is distant from the 4th century BC.

The following fragment gives more details and places Alexander in contact with the Amazons through a letter sent by the Macedonian ruler before entering their territory, although it does not specify the location.⁵⁴ No doubt hoping to avoid a confrontation before his conquest, and perhaps thinking that his fame would guarantee a tough fight for the Macedonians, he tried to intimidate the Amazon queen by listing all his exploits. He claimed that he had no intention of attacking them, only of getting to know their land and forming an alliance that would be mutually beneficial. Far from being impressed, the reply, presumably written by their sovereign, was no less grandiloquent, noting that few could surpass her in prestige and inviting such arrogant foreigners to cease and desist if they did not wish to be defeated.

The description she gives of her homeland and the hardships the conquest would entail will not be analysed here, as it is even more exaggerated than in other accounts and was only intended to frighten the Macedonians, although this is the first time they are turned into narrators of their own customs. Nevertheless, the letter ends with an interesting note. Aware that such a mighty conqueror could not help but seek glory in all that he did, they remind him that defeat would bring him greater embarrassment and his possible victory no prestige, for they were, after all, only a group of women.

Her cunning allowed him to avoid a confrontation that was merely a response to the Macedonian's desire to be on a par with the greatest heroes of antiquity. However, Alexander had to conceal his retreat if he did not want to be branded a coward, so he decided to continue his march to the Amazonian frontier, which the author places at the Pritanis River.⁵⁵ We do not know the location of this river, as he only adds that it poured its waters into Pontus from Anatolia (perhaps the Thermodon). In the absence of Amazons on their route, it seems that the main difficulty they encountered was the weather, which was very similar to the characteristics of the monsoon they faced in India. Undoubtedly, it was necessary to provide these lands with conditions appropriate to their marginal character. After overcoming these difficulties, Alexander reached the fertile plain of Pritanis (probably the plain of Themyscira), where they were finally able to meet the warriors.⁵⁶

His description of the Amazons is based on the usual flattery of their intelligence, cunning, incomparable beauty, tall stature and outstanding courage, although he emphasises their colourful costumes, an allusion that we can relate to the image offered by Hellanicus, who refers to their gold shields and silver axes.⁵⁷ Pseudo-Chalithenes states that they did not know iron or bronze, a claim shared by Apollonius with regard to iron, although he points out that their neighbours, the Chalyptians, worked it and were able to obtain it from them⁵⁸. In fact, Hellanicus contradicts himself

kingdom and, therefore, following traditions that refer to Thermodon and not to the river Phasis, Hyrcania or northern Pontus.

⁵⁰ Hdt. 4.136. Hanks (2000, 27) states that horse riding and archery have their origins in the nomadic peoples of the Eurasian steppes.

⁵¹ Ps. Callisth. 3. 19.

⁵² They were a people who lived in Bithynia. According to Strabo (7. 3, 2), one of the many Thracian tribes that had crossed into Asia from the eastern border of the Hellenic territory (Sanchez Sanz 2024b, 3).

⁵³ Str. 7.3.2.

⁵⁴ Ps. Callisth. 3. 25.

⁵⁵ Ps. Callisth. 3. 27.

⁵⁶ Ps. Callisth. 3. 27.

⁵⁷ Hellanicus (cfr. Tz. *AH*. 23). Xenophon (Ann. 4) also stated that they used axes.

⁵⁸ A. R. 2. 378-390.

by recalling that the Amazons burned their right breast with a red-hot iron, although he doubts this practice.⁵⁹ On the other hand, the allusion to their dress undoubtedly refers to the typical oriental costumes so common in these latitudes and, above all, to Amazonian iconography, although it contradicts the description of the *chitoniskos* offered by Rufus⁶⁰. The passage ends by placing the Macedonian on the banks of the river that served as a border, without crossing it and waiting for events to unfold⁶¹. He describes the river as imposing and surrounded by a multitude of wild animals, in order to emphasise the mythical and indomitable character of the land.

The end of this story is part of another, no less surprising passage, which states that Alexander received the expected tribute from the Amazons and withdrew without fighting⁶². Apparently, with only the river between the two armies, a fierce battle was in the offing, which the Amazons ultimately avoided by surrendering, perhaps aware that they would not be able to resist the seasoned Macedonian troops. This is the first known mention of these warriors avoiding battle, no doubt for the greater glory of the Macedonian ruler. More interestingly, Pseudo-Callisthenes never mentions the union of the two monarchs, let alone the thirteen days of procreation. The last known reference is by Orosius⁶³, although he adds little to Trogo's summary, offering only two possibilities for the queen's name, which we can understand as corruptions of those already mentioned.⁶⁴ He states that she went in search of Alexander with three hundred female warriors, a recurring figure and perhaps related to other famous military units of antiquity, such as the sacred Theban battalion⁶⁵ or the Spartan guard assigned to their rulers⁶⁶, which could also respond to a demonstration of power or a lack of confidence in the Macedonians. Their mission was to provide the Macedonian king with an heiress, adding only that the meeting took place in the territory of the Sicans and Mardes.⁶⁷

3. Conclusion

The story of Alexander and Thalestris shows an important homogeneity that is rarely found in the mythical universe of the Amazon, apart from distortions, additions or lesser-known traditions and, of course, the obvious scepticism of many authors. Its appearance is much later than expected, at least as far as the main Amazon myths are concerned, with the peculiarity of referring to a historical figure, which may have contributed to reducing the diversity of versions. It seems that sometime between 330 and 324 BC, when the Macedonian army was near the border with Hyrcania, a group of Amazons asked to meet Alexander III.

The embassy was led by their sovereign, Thalestris, who explained her intentions and remained at his side for thirteen days before returning to her homeland. Most of these details are canonical, including the lack of information about the success of the meeting. After that, Alexander went on his way and the Amazon returned to her homeland without our knowing about her success, even if it was relative (male child). Only other kinds of consequences related to Alexander himself, resulting from the influence of the Amazon, are alluded to. The moralising intent of these statements has sometimes been defended⁶⁸, although, if true, it is likely that they were present in a larger number of traditions.⁶⁹

Be that as it may, there is no doubt about the legendary nature of this event, as Lysimachus himself ironically points out⁷⁰, although we do not know whether it appears in the work of Clitarchus⁷¹, which he would have collected from Onesicritus⁷², or whether we can attribute it to Polyclitus of Larissa⁷³. Both were part of the expedition, but defending such events would undoubtedly have damaged their credibility as chroniclers, especially as many of those present would live long enough to deny it, as they did. For this reason, it is perhaps more plausible to attribute their authorship to Clitarchus' own initiative, or even to the unknown Origen or Istro, since they were not part

⁵⁹ Hellanicus (cf. Tz. *AH*. 23).

⁶⁰ Curt. 6. 5. 24-32.

⁶¹ Ps. Callisth. 3. 27.

⁶² Ps. Callisth. 3. 27.

⁶³ Oros. 3. 18. 5.

⁶⁴ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 181-182.

⁶⁵ Plu. *Pel.* 28, 1.

⁶⁶ Hdt. 7. 202.

⁶⁷ Verg. *Aen.* 11. 651-665.

⁶⁸ Daumas 1992, 350.

⁶⁹ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 186.

⁷⁰ Plu. *Alex.* 46.

⁷¹ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 182; Hammond 1983, 293, note 27.

⁷² Fox 1973, 531; Goukowsky 1980, 139, note 1.

⁷³ Tarn 1948, 328; Pearson 1960, 75, note 17.

of the expedition. Only Arrian⁷⁴ and Plutarch⁷⁵ evade this tradition by offering accounts that have nothing to do with it. In fact, Plutarch may have been trying to explore the possibility that this episode was based on real events mythologised by one of these authors, such as the proposal of the Scythian king or the gift of Atrophates.

The problem arises when other authors who also cite this possible link, such as Curtius⁷⁶ or Arrian⁷⁷, do not establish a relationship between the two episodes and treat them independently. A rationalist analysis would give more credibility to Arrian's account⁷⁸, similarly offered by Polyclitus and Onesicritus, and distorted by another source such as Clitarchus, Istrous and/or Origen, perhaps to enhance the figure of the Macedonian, each one choosing the version he considered most plausible if he had both or only the one he could consult. An encounter with female warriors, whether or not they were considered Amazons, could not have been denied by Lysimachus, for it would certainly have been an experience worth remembering by those who witnessed it.⁷⁹ Even if we believe Arrian, and that the existence of a queen among them could point to a common source unknown to us, Trogo's version would again imply the existence of a group of armed women.

Perhaps both authors, or at least one of them, although part of the expedition, decided to embellish their account, or they were simply not present at the time and inserted it later, distorting it so that Lysimachus was unable to recognise it. Nor can it be ruled out that a group of Macedonian soldiers, on patrol or on some kind of mission (logically without Lysimachus), came into contact with women belonging to the nomadic tribes of those regions, who proved to be skilled horsemen and warriors, so that the story they told on their return eventually gave rise to the accounts we know⁸⁰.

In any case, the aim of this story was to enhance the prestige of the Macedonian ruler by using the same traditional recourse to other heroes, which is very appropriate when we are talking about this region⁸¹, and even more so in the case of mythical figures associated with the heroic past that he so admired and tried to emulate.⁸² Indirectly, all these versions imply a subordinate female image, while at the same time emphasizing the masculinity of the Macedonian, helping to negate the claims of those who defended his indifference towards the female gender⁸³, even if this was not the ultimate aim of the passage. Whatever the outcome, it was a win-win situation, with the Amazons gaining an heir to restore their lost glory and Alexander gaining a worthy offspring. However, only Justin explains that the Amazon became pregnant⁸⁴, without even hinting at a happy outcome or that the fruit would play a role in subsequent events, so the narrative merely responds to this desire for mythification.⁸⁵

⁷⁴ Arr. *An.* 7. 14.

⁷⁵ Plu. *Alex.* 46.

⁷⁶ Curt. 8. 1. 9.

⁷⁷ Arr. *An.* 4. 15. 2.

⁷⁸ Domínguez Monedero 2000, 183.

⁷⁹ In spite of this, Cadogan (1910, 62) gives some veracity to the story, indicating that it could be a branch of the Amazon people developed in the Caucasus region.

⁸⁰ For Davis-Kimball (2002, 235) nomadic societies egalitarianism would have prevailed over the typical patriarchal system.

⁸¹ Goukowsky 1980, 139, note 1.

⁸² Whalley 2010, 65.

⁸³ Plu. *Alex.* 21.

⁸⁴ Iust. *Epit.* 12. 3. 7.

⁸⁵ As Domínguez Monedero shares (2000, 185).

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